

RESEARCH ARTICLE

A New Class of Generalized Closed Sets in Pentapartitioned Neutrosophic Topological Spaces

Received: 29-08-2023

Accepted: 05-03-2024

Published: 25-05-2024

Editor: ICDMMMDE-2023 Special Issue Editors: Dr. G. Mahadevan and Prof. Dr. P. Balasubramaniam

Citation: Jackson S, Sivasankar J (2024) A New Class of Generalized Closed Sets in Pentapartitioned Neutrosophic Topological Spaces. Indian Journal of Science and Technology 17(SP1): 14-20. <https://doi.org/10.17485/IJST/v17sp1.113>

* **Corresponding author.**
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Funding: None

Competing Interests: None

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Published By Indian Society for Education and Environment ([ISEE](https://www.isee.org/))

ISSN

Print: 0974-6846

Electronic: 0974-5645

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Abstract

Objective: The motive of this research paper is to give a new notion called Pentapartitioned Neutrosophic Generalized Pre Open and Closed sets.

Methods: To get the Pentapartitioned Neutrosophic Generalized Pre Open and Closed sets, PN topology is needed. Further, there is a need to find the Pre Open and Pre Closed sets and then we use our definition to get the required objective. **Findings:** The Pentapartitioned Neutrosophic Generalized Pre sets give a more finer collection of weak sets. Moreover, we can find the interior, exterior, and frontier of the resultant set. **Novelty:** Finding the generalized part of Pentapartitioned Neutrosophic sets is a subtle work to do. So, the investigation procedure of its characterization is an interesting aspect.

Keywords: Pentapartitioned Neutrosophic Generalized Pre Closed Set; Pentapartitioned Neutrosophic Frontier; Pentapartitioned Neutrosophic Pre Frontier of a Pentapartitioned Neutrosophic Set; Pentapartitioned Neutrosophic Set and Pentapartitioned Neutrosophic Pre

1 Introduction

Pentapartitioned Neutrosophic Generalized Pre Open sets and Pentapartitioned Neutrosophic Generalized Pre Closed sets are the main ideas presented in this research paper. Neutrosophic sets, a new type of generalized intuitionistic fuzzy sets, were introduced in 2005 by Florentin Smarandache. Further Salama and Alblowi opened a new topological space involving Neutrosophic sets. Our paper takes the Five Single Valued Neutrosophic Logic(FSVNL) or simply Pentapartitioned Neutrosophic fuzzy logic as the core. In 2020, Rama Mallick and Surapathi Pramanik⁽¹⁾ introduced the Pentapartitioned Neutrosophic sets and their properties. In the path of them, Suman Das and Binod Chandra Tripathy⁽²⁾ deeply investigated the topology formed by the Pentapartitioned Neutrosophic Sets in 2020. In this research paper, we study some of the characteristics of Pentapartitioned Neutrosophic Pre *Open* and *Closed* sets like, interior, closure, frontier, and exterior.

Research gap: In the most recent body of research, many authors made their studies in Pentapartitioned Neutrosophic Topological Spaces but no study on Pentapartitioned Neutrosophic Generalized Pre open and closed sets of pentapartitioned neutrosophic topological space has been reported.

2 Methodology

This section presents Pentapartitioned Neutrosophic Sets and topology, null set, absolute set and basic properties to formulate the Generalized sets. Throughout this study, τ_{PN} stands for Topology induced by a Pentapartitioned Neutrosophic set.

Definition 2.1⁽³⁾ Consider Z as a non-empty set. A Neutrosophic set R over Z is defined as $R = \{(r, T_R(r), I_R(r), F_R(r)) / r \in Z\}$ where $T, I, F : Z \rightarrow [0, 1]$, represents the degree of Truth Membership, Indeterminacy Membership and False Membership functions respectively and $0 \leq T_R(r) + I_R(r) + F_R(r) \leq 3$ for each $r \in Z$.

Definition 2.2⁽⁴⁾ Consider Z as a universal set. A Pentapartitioned Neutrosophic Set (PN set) R over Z is a 6-tuple of the form, $R = \{(r, T_R(r), C_R(r), G_R(r), U_R(r), F_R(r)) / r \in Z\}$ where $T, C, G, U, F : Z \rightarrow [0, 1]$, represents the degree of the Truth Membership, Contradiction Membership, Ignorance Membership, Unknown Membership and Falsity Membership functions respectively and $0 \leq T_R(r) + C_R(r) + G_R(r) + U_R(r) + F_R(r) \leq 5$ for each $r \in Z$.

Definition 2.3⁽⁵⁾ Consider R, S be two Pentapartitioned Neutrosophic sets over Z .

i) $R \subseteq S$ if and only if $T_R(r) \leq T_S(r), C_R(r) \leq C_S(r), G_R(r) \geq G_S(r), U_R(r) \geq U_S(r), F_R(r) \geq F_S(r)$ for each $r \in Z$.

ii) $R \cup S = \{(r, \max(T_R(r), T_S(r)), \max(C_R(r), C_S(r)), \min(G_R(r), G_S(r)), \min(U_R(r), U_S(r)), \min(F_R(r), F_S(r))) / r \in Z\}$.

iii) $R \cap S = \{(r, \min(T_R(r), T_S(r)), \min(C_R(r), C_S(r)), \max(G_R(r), G_S(r)),$

$$\max(U_R(r), U_S(r)), \max(F_R(r), F_S(r))) / r \in Z\}.$$

iv) If $R = \{(r, T_R(r), C_R(r), G_R(r), U_R(r), F_R(r)) / r \in Z\}$,

then $R^C = \{(r, F_R(r), U_R(r), 1 - (G_R(r)), C_R(r), T_R(r)) / r \in Z\}$.

v) $R \not\subseteq S$ if atleast one of the following occurs $T_R(r) \geq T_S(r), C_R(r) \geq C_S(r), G_R(r) \leq G_S(r), U_R(r) \leq U_S(r), F_R(r) \leq F_S(r)$ for any $r \in Z$.

vi) $R \neq S$ if $R \not\subseteq S$ and $S \not\subseteq R$.

Definition 2.4⁽⁶⁾ A Pentapartitioned Neutrosophic set over Z is called as Null Pentapartitioned Neutrosophic set if, $T_D(a) = 0, C_D(a) = 0, G_D(a) = 1, U_D(a) = 1, F_D(a) = 1$. We denote the Null Pentapartitioned Neutrosophic set by 0_{PN} . That is $0_{PN} = \{(a, 0, 0, 1, 1, 1) / a \in Z\}$.

Definition 2.5⁽⁶⁾ A Pentapartitioned Neutrosophic set over Z is called as Absolute Pentapartitioned Neutrosophic set if, $T_D(a) = 1, C_D(a) = 1, G_D(a) = 0, U_D(a) = 0, F_D(a) = 0$. We denote the Absolute Pentapartitioned Neutrosophic set by 1_{PN} . That is $1_{PN} = \{(a, 1, 1, 0, 0, 0) / a \in Z\}$.

Definition 2.6⁽²⁾ Consider Z be the universal set. Then the collection τ_{PN} of Pentapartitioned Neutrosophic sets over Z is known as a Pentapartitioned Neutrosophic Topology on Z , if the following conditions are satisfied.

1. $0_{PN}, 1_{PN} \in \tau_{PN}$
2. $P, Q \in \tau_{PN}$ then $P \cap Q \in \tau_{PN}$
3. $\{P_i / i \in I\} \in \tau_{PN}$ then $\cup_{i \in I} P_i \in \tau_{PN}$

The pair (Z, τ_{PN}) is named as the Pentapartitioned Neutrosophic Topological Space. Each element of τ_{PN} is called a Pentapartitioned Neutrosophic *Open* Sets. If $L \in \tau_{PN}$, then L^c is called as Pentapartitioned Neutrosophic (for simply PN) *Closed* Set.

Definition 2.7⁽⁷⁾ Consider (Z, τ_{PN}) a Pentapartitioned Neutrosophic Topological space. Let W be a Pentapartitioned Neutrosophic set over Z . Then PN-interior of W is the Union of PN-*Open* sets of (Z, τ_{PN}) contained in W and is denoted by $\text{PN-int}(W)$. That is $\text{PN-int}(W) = \cup \{U / U \subseteq W \text{ and } U \text{ is a PN-Open set in } (Z, \tau_{PN})\}$.

Definition 2.8⁽²⁾ Consider (Z, τ_{PN}) a Pentapartitioned Neutrosophic Topological space. Let W be Pentapartitioned Neutrosophic set over Z . Then PN-closure of W is the Intersection of PN-*closed* sets of (Z, τ_{PN}) containing W and is denoted by $\text{PN-cl}(W)$. That is $\text{PN-cl}(W) = \cap \{U / W \subseteq U \text{ and } U \text{ is a PN-Closed set in } (Z, \tau_{PN})\}$.

Remark 2.9 If W is Pentapartitioned Neutrosophic *Open* set in a PN Topological space (Z, τ_{PN}) , then $\text{PN-int}(W) = W$. If W is Pentapartitioned Neutrosophic *Closed* set in a PN Topological space (Z, τ_{PN}) , then $\text{PN-cl}(W) = W$.

Definition 2.10⁽⁸⁾ Consider (Z, τ_{PN}) a Pentapartitioned Neutrosophic Topological Space. A Pentapartitioned Neutrosophic set R over Z is known as,

- (i) PN regular *open* if $R = \text{PN-int}[\text{PN-cl}(R)]$
- (ii) PN regular *closed* if $R = \text{PN-cl}[\text{PN-int}(R)]$.

Definition 2.11⁽²⁾ Consider (Z, τ_{PN}) a Pentapartitioned Neutrosophic Topological space. Then a Pentapartitioned Neutrosophic set R is known as,

- (i) PN-Semi Open set if and only if $R \subseteq \text{PN-cl} [\text{PN-int} (R)]$.
- (ii) PN- α Open set if and only if $R \subseteq \text{PN-int} (\text{PN-cl} (\text{PN-int} (R)))$.

Definition 2.12 Consider (Z, τ_{PN}) a Pentapartitioned Neutrosophic Topological space. Then a Pentapartitioned Neutrosophic Set R is known as,

- (i) PN-SemiClosed set if and only if $\text{PN-int} [\text{PN-cl} (R)] \subseteq R$.
- (ii) PN- α Closed set if and only if $\text{PN-cl} (\text{PN-int} (\text{PN-cl} (R))) \subseteq R$.

3 Results and Discussion

3.1 PN Pre Interior and PN Pre Closure of a PN set

Definition 3.1. 1 A PN set M is taken from PN Topological space (Z, τ_{PN}) . Then M is called PN Pre ClosedSet in (Z, τ_{PN}) if and only if $\text{PN-cl} [\text{PN-int} (M)] \subseteq M$.

Definition 3.1.2⁽²⁾ A PN set M is taken from PN Topological space (Z, τ_{PN}) . Then M is called PN Pre Open set in (Z, τ_{PN}) if and only if $M \subseteq \text{PN-int} [\text{PN-cl} (M)]$.

Definition 3.1. 3 For any PN set M in a PN Topological Space (Z, τ_{PN}) , PN Pre-interior of M is defined as the Union of all PN Pre Open sets contained in M . That is,

$$\text{PN Pre - int } M = \cup \{D \subseteq (Z, \tau_{PN}) / D \subseteq M \text{ and } D \text{ is a PN Pre Open set}\}$$

Definition 3.1. 4 For any PN set M in a PN Topological Space (Z, τ_{PN}) , PN Pre-closure of M is defined as the Intersection of all PN Pre Closed sets containing M . That is,

$$\text{PN Pre - cl } M = \cap \{D \subseteq (Z, \tau_{PN}) / M \subseteq D \text{ and } D \text{ is a PN Pre Closed set}\}$$

Proposition 3.1.5 Consider M a PN set over a PN Topological space (Z, τ_{PN}) . Then

- 1. $[\text{PN Pre - int } M]^C = \text{PN Pre - cl } M^C$
- 2. $[\text{PN Pre - cl } M]^C = \text{PN Pre - int } M^C$

Proof:

1. By considering M as a PN set over a PN Topological space (Z, τ_{PN}) , we have $\text{PN Pre - int } M = \cup \{G / G \text{ is a PN Pre Open set and } G \subseteq M\}$.

Then $[\text{PN Pre - int } M]^C = [\cup \{G / G \text{ is a PN Pre Open set and } G \subseteq M\}]^C = \cap \{G^C / G^C \text{ is a PN Pre Closed set and } G^C \supseteq M^C\}$. Taking G^C as S , we get, $[\text{PN Pre - int } M]^C = \cap \{S / S \text{ is a PN Pre Closed set and } S \supseteq M^C\}$. Thus, $[\text{PN Pre - int } M]^C = \text{PN Pre - cl } M^C$.

2. By considering M as a PN set over a PN Topological space (Z, τ_{PN}) . Now, $\text{PN Pre - cl } M = \cap \{H / H \text{ is a PN Pre Closed set and } H \supseteq M\}$. Then $[\text{PN Pre - cl } M]^C = [\cap \{H / H \text{ is a PN Pre Closed set and } H \supseteq M\}]^C = \cup \{H^C / H^C \text{ is a PN Pre Open set and } H^C \subseteq M^C\}$. Taking H^C as S , we get $[\text{PN Pre - cl } M]^C = \cup \{S / S \text{ is a PN Pre Open set and } S \subseteq M^C\}$. Thus, $[\text{PN Pre - cl } M]^C = \text{PN Pre - int } M^C$.

Theorem 3.1 .6 Consider (Z, τ_{PN}) a PN Topological space. Then for any two PN sets L and Q over a PN Topological space (Z, τ_{PN}) we have, $\text{PN Pre - int} (L \cap Q) = (\text{PN Pre - int } L) \cap (\text{PN Pre - int } Q)$.

Proof:

Let (Z, τ_{PN}) be a PN Topological space. Let L and Q be any two PN sets over a PN Topological space (Z, τ_{PN}) . By the property of PN sets, $L \cap Q \subseteq L$ and $L \cap Q \subseteq Q$. Then we have $\text{PN Pre - int} (L \cap Q) \subseteq (\text{PN Pre - int } L)$ and $\text{PN Pre - int} (L \cap Q) \subseteq (\text{PN Pre - int } Q)$. Therefore $\text{PN Pre - int} (L \cap Q) \subseteq (\text{PN Pre - int } L) \cap (\text{PN Pre - int } Q)$ ---(1)

Now, $(\text{PN Pre - int } L) \subseteq L$ and $(\text{PN Pre - int } Q) \subseteq Q$. Then $(\text{PN Pre - int } L) \cap (\text{PN Pre - int } Q) \subseteq L \cap Q$. By we have $\text{PN Pre - int} [(L \cap Q)] \subseteq \text{PN Pre - int} (L \cap Q)$. Thus $(\text{PN Pre - int } L) \cap (\text{PN Pre - int } Q) \subseteq \text{PN Pre - int} (L \cap Q)$ ---(2)

From (1) and (2) we get,

$$\text{PN Pre - int} (L \cap Q) = (\text{PN Pre - int } L) \cap (\text{PN Pre - int } Q)$$

Theorem 3.1 .7 Consider (Z, τ_{PN}) a PN Topological space. Then for any two PN sets L and Q over a PN Topological space (Z, τ_{PN}) we have, $\text{PN Pre - int} (L \cup Q) \supseteq (\text{PN Pre - int } L) \cup (\text{PN Pre - int } Q)$.

Proof:

Consider (Z, τ_{PN}) as a PN Topological space. Let L and Q be any two PN sets over a PN Topological space (Z, τ_{PN}) . By the property of PN sets we have $L \subseteq L \cup Q$ and $Q \subseteq L \cup Q$. Then we have $(\text{PN Pre - int } L) \subseteq \text{PN Pre - int} (L \cup Q)$ and $(\text{PN Pre - int } Q) \subseteq \text{PN Pre - int} (L \cup Q)$. Therefore $(\text{PN Pre - int } L) \cup (\text{PN Pre - int } Q) \subseteq \text{PN Pre - int} (L \cup Q)$.

Theorem 3.1.8 Consider (Z, τ_{PN}) a PN Topological space. Then for any two PN sets L and Q over a PN Topological space (Z, τ_{PN}) we have, $\text{PN Pre-cl}(L \cup Q) = (\text{PN Pre-cl} L) \cup (\text{PN Pre-cl} Q)$.

Proof:

Consider (Z, τ_{PN}) a PN Topological space. Let L and R be any two PN sets over a PN Topological space (Z, τ_{PN}) . We have $\text{PN Pre-cl}(L \cup R) = \text{PN Pre-cl}([(L \cup R)^C]^C)$. Then $\text{PN Pre-cl}(L \cup R) = [\text{PN Pre-int}(L \cup R)^C]^C$. Also we have $\text{PN Pre-cl}(L \cup R) = [\text{PN Pre-int}(L^C \cap R^C)]^C$. This implies $\text{PN Pre-cl}(L \cup R) = [\text{PN Pre-int}(L^C) \cap \text{PN Pre-int}(R^C)]^C$. Again we have $\text{PN Pre-cl}(L \cup R) = [\text{PN Pre-int}(L^C)]^C \cup [\text{PN Pre-int}(R^C)]^C$. Thus we have $\text{PN Pre-cl}(L \cup R) = [\text{PN Pre-cl}(L)] \cup [\text{PN Pre-cl}(R)]$.

Theorem 3.1.9 Consider (Z, τ_{PN}) a PN Topological space. Then for any two PN sets P and Q over a PN Topological space (Z, τ_{PN}) we have, $\text{PN Pre-cl}(P \cap Q) \subseteq (\text{PN Pre-cl} P) \cap (\text{PN Pre-cl} Q)$.

Proof:

Consider (Z, τ_{PN}) be a PN Topological space. Let P and Q be any two PN sets over a PN Topological space (Z, τ_{PN}) . By the property of PN sets, $P \cap Q \subseteq P$ and $P \cap Q \subseteq Q$. Then we have $\text{PN Pre-cl}(P \cap Q) \subseteq (\text{PN Pre-cl} P)$ and $\text{PN Pre-cl}(P \cap Q) \subseteq (\text{PN Pre-cl} Q)$. This implies $\text{PN Pre-cl}(P \cap Q) \subseteq (\text{PN Pre-cl} P) \cap (\text{PN Pre-cl} Q)$.

Definition 3.1.10 A PN set M is taken from PN Topological Space (Z, τ_{PN}) . Then PN exterior of M in (Z, τ_{PN}) is defined as PN exterior $(M) = \text{PN-int}(M^C)$

Definition 3.1.11 A PN set M is taken from PN Topological Space (Z, τ_{PN}) . Then PN

Pre exterior of M in (Z, τ_{PN}) is defined as PN Pre exterior $(M) = \text{PN Pre-int}(M^C)$

Definition 3.1.12 A PN set M is taken from PN Topological Space (Z, τ_{PN}) . Then PN frontier of M in (Z, τ_{PN}) is defined as PN frontier $(M) = \text{PN-cl}(M) \cap \text{PN-cl}(M^C)$

Definition 3.1.13 A PN set M is taken from PN Topological Space (Z, τ_{PN}) . Then PN Pre frontier of M in (Z, τ_{PN}) is defined as PN Pre frontier $(M) = \text{PN Pre-cl}(M) \cap \text{PN Pre-cl}(M^C)$

3.2 PN Generalized Pre Closed Set

Definition 3.2.1 A PN set M is taken from PN Topological space (Z, τ_{PN}) . Then M is said to be a PN Generalized Pre Closed set in (Z, τ_{PN}) if $\text{PN Pre-cl}(M) \subseteq K$ whenever $M \subseteq K$ and K is a PN open set.

Theorem 3.2.2 Every PN Pre Closed set in a PN Topological space (Z, τ_{PN}) is PN Generalized Pre Closed set.

Proof:

Let J be a PN Pre Closed set. Then $\text{PN Pre-cl}(J) = J$ ---(i). And if $J \subseteq K$ by (i), we get $\text{PN Pre-cl}(J) \subseteq K$. From definition 3.2.1, we conclude J is a PN Generalized Pre Closed set. Converse part of Theorem 3.2.2 is need not be True.

Theorem 3.2.3 Every PN Closed set in a PN Topological space (Z, τ_{PN}) is PN Generalized Pre Closed set.

Proof:

Consider J be a PN Closed set. Then $\text{PN-cl}(J) = J$ ---(i). We know, always $\text{PN-int}(J) \subseteq J$. This implies $\text{PN-cl}(\text{PN-int}(J)) \subseteq \text{PN-cl}(J)$ by (i) we get, $\text{PN-cl}(\text{PN-int}(J)) \subseteq J$. Therefore, J is a PN Pre Closed set. Also from Theorem 3.2.2 we get, J is a PN Generalized Pre Closed set.

Converse part of Theorem 3.2.3 is need not be True.

Example 3.2.4 Consider $X = \{p\}$ and E, F be two Pentapartitioned Neutrosophic sets over X such that, $E = \{(p, 0.5, 0.4, 0.9, 0.8, 0.7)\}$ and $F = \{(p, 0.6, 0.7, 0.7, 0.3, 0.4)\}$. Then $\tau_{PN} = \{0, 1, E, F\}$ forms a Pentapartitioned Neutrosophic Topology. Also, $E^C = \{(p, 0.7, 0.8, 0.1, 0.4, 0.5)\}$ $F^C = \{(p, 0.4, 0.3, 0.3, 0.7, 0.6)\}$. Since E and F are PN open sets, $\text{PN-int}(E) = E$, $\text{PN-int}(E^C) = E$, $\text{PN-int}(F) = F$, $\text{PN-int}(F^C) = 0$, $\text{PN-cl}(E) = E^C$, $\text{PN-cl}(E^C) = E^C$, $\text{PN-cl}(F) = 1$ and $\text{PN-cl}(F^C) = F^C$.

Now $T = \{(p, 0.5, 0.6, 0.3, 0.7, 0.6)\}$ is a Pentapartitioned Neutrosophic set over X . Since $\text{PN-int}(T) = E$, $\text{PN-cl}(T) = E^C$ and $\text{PN-cl}(\text{PN-int}(T)) = \text{PN-cl}(E) = E^C$. Then $E^C \not\subseteq T$. Thus T is not a PN Pre Closed set. Also E^C is the smallest PN Pre Closed set containing T , therefore $\text{PN Pre-cl} T = E^C$. Also, $T \subseteq 1$ then we get $\text{PN Pre-cl} T = E^C \subseteq 1$, where 1 is PN Open set. Therefore, T is a PN Generalized Pre Closed set.

Now $M = \{(p, 0.6, 0.5, 0.4, 0.4, 0.6)\}$ is a Pentapartitioned Neutrosophic set over X . Since $\text{PN-int}(M) = E$, $\text{PN-cl}(M) = E^C$ then M is not a PN Closed set. And $\text{PN-cl}(\text{PN-int}(M)) = \text{PN-cl}(E) = E^C$. Then $E^C \not\subseteq M$. Thus M is not a PN Pre Closed set. Also E^C is the smallest PN Pre Closed set containing M , therefore $\text{PN Pre-cl} M = E^C$. Also, $M \subseteq 1$ then we get $\text{PN Pre-cl} M = E^C \subseteq 1$, where 1 is PN Open set. Therefore, M is a PN Generalized Pre Closed set.

Definition 3.2.5 A PN set M is taken from PN Topological space (Z, τ_{PN}) . Then M is called PN Generalized Pre Open set in (Z, τ_{PN}) if $K \subseteq \text{PN Pre-int}(M)$ whenever $K \subseteq M$ and K is a PN closed set.

Example 3.2.6 Consider $X = \{p\}$ and D, E be two Pentapartitioned Neutrosophic sets over X such that, $D = \{(p, 0.4, 0.3, 0.6, 0.7, 0.5)\}$ and $E = \{(p, 0.5, 0.5, 0.5, 0.4, 0.2)\}$. Then $\tau_{PN} = \{0, 1, D, E\}$ forms a Pentapartitioned

Neutrosophic Topology. Also, $D^C = \{(p, 0.5, 0.7, 0.4, 0.3, 0.4)\}$ $E^C = \{(p, 0.2, 0.4, 0.5, 0.5, 0.5)\}$. Since D and E are PN open sets, $\text{PN-int}(D)=D$, $\text{PN-int}(D^C)=D$, $\text{PN-int}(E)=E$, $\text{PN-int}(E^C)=0$, $\text{PN-cl}(D)=D^C$, $\text{PN-cl}(D^C)=D^C$, $\text{PN-cl}(E)=1$ and $\text{PN-cl}(E^C)=E^C$.

Now $M = \{(p, 0.7, 0.5, 0.6, 0.1, 0.3)\}$ is a Pentapartitioned Neutrosophic set over X . Since $\text{PN-int}(M)=D$, $\text{PN-cl}(M)=1$ and $\text{PN-int}(\text{PN-cl}(M))=\text{PN-int}(1)=1$. Then $M \subseteq 1$. Thus M is a PN Pre Open set. Also M is the largest PN Pre Open set contained in M , therefore $\text{PN Pre-int } M=M$. Hence, if $M \subseteq U$ then we get $\text{PN Pre-int } M \subseteq U$, where U is PN Closed set. Therefore, M is a PN Generalized Pre Open set.

Remark 3.2.7 Complement of a PN Generalized Pre Closed set is PN Generalized Pre Open set and viceversa.

Theorem 3.2.8 Every PN Pre Open set in a PN Topological space (Z, τ_{PN}) is PN Generalized Pre Open set.

Proof:

Let J be a PN Pre Open set. Then $\text{PN Pre-int}(J)=J$ ---(i). And if $M \subset J$ by (i), we get $M \subset \text{PN Pre-int}(J)$. Thus we conclude J is a PN Generalized Pre Open set. Converse part of Theorem 3.2.7 is need not be True.

Theorem 3.2.9 Every PN Open set in a PN Topological space (Z, τ_{PN}) is PN Generalized Pre Open set.

Proof:

Let J be a PN Open set. Then $\text{PN-int}(J)=J$ ---(i). We know, always $J \subseteq \text{PN-cl}(J)$. This implies $\text{PN-int}(J) \subseteq \text{PN-int}(\text{PN-cl}(J))$ by (i) we get, $J \subseteq \text{PN-int}(\text{PN-cl}(J))$. Therefore, J is a PN Pre Open set. Also from Theorem 3.2.8 of this section we get, J is a PN Generalized Pre Open set. Converse part of Theorem 3.2.8 is need not be True.

Example 3.2.10 Consider $X = \{p\}$ and E, F be two Pentapartitioned Neutrosophic sets over X such that, $E = \{(p, 0.5, 0.4, 0.9, 0.8, 0.7)\}$ and $F = \{(p, 0.6, 0.7, 0.7, 0.3, 0.4)\}$. Then $\tau_{PN} = \{0, 1, E, F\}$ forms a Pentapartitioned Neutrosophic Topology. Also, $E^C = \{(p, 0.7, 0.8, 0.1, 0.4, 0.5)\}$ $F^C = \{(p, 0.4, 0.3, 0.3, 0.7, 0.6)\}$. Since E and F are PN open sets, $\text{PN-int}(E)=E$, $\text{PN-int}(E^C)=E$, $\text{PN-int}(F)=F$, $\text{PN-int}(F^C)=0$, $\text{PN-cl}(E)=E^C$, $\text{PN-cl}(E^C)=E^C$, $\text{PN-cl}(F)=1$ and $\text{PN-cl}(F^C)=F^C$.

Now $R = \{(p, 0.5, 0.5, 0.5, 0.5, 0.5)\}$ is a Pentapartitioned Neutrosophic set over X . Since $\text{PN-int}(R)=E$, $\text{PN-cl}(R)=E^C$ and $\text{PN-int}(\text{PN-cl}(R))=\text{PN-int}(E^C)=E$. Then $R \not\subseteq E$. Thus R is not a PN Pre Open set. Also E is the largest PN Pre Open set contained in R , therefore $\text{PN Pre-int } R=E$. Also, $0 \subseteq R$ then we get $0 \subseteq E=\text{PN Pre-int } R$, where 0 is PN Closed set. Therefore, R is a PN Generalized Pre Open set.

Now $S = \{(p, 0.7, 0.7, 0.3, 0.5, 0.6)\}$ is a Pentapartitioned Neutrosophic set over X . Since $\text{PN-int}(S)=E$, $\text{PN-cl}(S)=E^C$ then S is not a PN Open set. And $\text{PN-int}(\text{PN-cl}(S))=\text{PN-int}(E^C)=E$. Then $S \not\subseteq E$. Thus S is not a PN Pre Open set. Also E is the largest PN Pre Open set contained in S , therefore $\text{PN Pre-int } S=E$. Also, $0 \subseteq S$ then we get $0 \subseteq E=\text{PN Pre-int } S$, where 0 is PN Closed set. Therefore, S is a PN Generalized Pre Open set.

Definition 3.2.11 The PN Generalized Pre-interior of any PN set M in a PN Topological Space (Z, τ_{PN}) is defined as the Union of all PN Generalized Pre Open sets Contained in M and denoted by $\text{PN Generalized Pre-int } M$.

That is, $\text{PN Generalized Pre-int } M = \cup \{K \subseteq (Z, \tau_{PN}) / K \subseteq M \text{ and } K \text{ is a PN Generalized Pre Open set}\}$

Definition 3.2.12 The PN Generalized Pre-closure of any PN set M in a PN Topological Space (Z, τ_{PN}) is defined as the Intersection of all PN Generalized Pre Closed sets Containing M and denoted by $\text{PN Generalized Pre-cl } M$.

That is, $\text{PN Generalized Pre-cl } M = \cap \{K \subseteq (Z, \tau_{PN}) / M \subseteq K \text{ and } K \text{ is a PN Generalized Pre Closed set}\}$

Proposition 3.2.13 Let J and K be two PN sets in a PN Topological Space (Z, τ_{PN}) . Then we have the following results.

- (i) $J \subseteq \text{PN Generalized Pre-cl } (J)$.
- (ii) J is a PN Generalized Pre Closed set in (Z, τ_{PN}) if and only if $\text{PN Generalized Pre-cl } (J) = J$.
- (iii) $\text{PN Generalized Pre-cl}(\text{PN Generalized Pre-cl}(J)) = \text{PN Generalized Pre-cl}(J)$
- (iv) If $J \subseteq K$ then $\text{PN Generalized Pre-cl } (J) \subseteq \text{PN Generalized Pre-cl } (K)$.

Proof:

(i) By Definition 3.2.11, $\text{PN Generalized Pre-cl } (J) = \cap \{S / S \text{ is a PN Generalized Pre Closed set and } J \subseteq S\}$. This implies $J \subseteq \text{PN Generalized Pre-cl } (J)$. Thus (i) holds.

(ii) Suppose $\text{PN Generalized Pre-cl } (J) = J$. Then $\cup \{R / R \text{ is a PN Generalized Pre Closed set and } J \subseteq R\} = J$. This implies that J is a PN Generalized Pre Closed set in (Z, τ_{PN}) .

Conversely, suppose J is a PN Generalized Pre Closed set in (Z, τ_{PN}) . Then $\cup \{R / R \text{ is a PN Generalized Pre Closed set and } J \subseteq R\} = J$. Therefore, by Definition 3.2.11, $\text{PN Generalized Pre-cl } (J) = J$. Thus (ii) holds.

(iii) For any PN set J , $\text{PN Generalized Pre-cl } (J)$ is a PN Generalized Pre Closed set in (Z, τ_{PN}) . Using (ii) we get, $\text{PN Generalized Pre-cl}(\text{PN Generalized Pre-cl}(J)) = \text{PN Generalized Pre-cl}(J)$. Thus (iii) holds.

(iv) Let $J \subseteq K$. Then $J \subseteq K \subseteq \text{PN Generalized Pre-cl } (K)$. From this we get $J \subseteq \text{PN Generalized Pre-cl } (K)$. This implies $\text{PN Generalized Pre-cl } (J) \subseteq \text{PN Generalized Pre-cl}(\text{PN Generalized Pre-cl}(K))$. Therefore by (iii) of this proposition $\text{PN Generalized Pre-cl}(\text{PN Generalized Pre-cl}(K)) = \text{PN Generalized Pre-cl}(K)$. Hence we get $\text{PN Generalized Pre-cl } (J) \subseteq \text{PN Generalized Pre-cl } (K)$.

Generalized Pre -cl (K). Thus (iv) holds.

Proposition 3.2.1 4 Consider J and K the two PN sets in a PN Topological Space (Z, τ_{PN}) . Then we have the following results.

- (i) PN Generalized Pre -int (J) $\subseteq J$.
- (ii) J is a PN Generalized Pre *Open* set in (Z, τ_{PN}) if and only if PN Generalized Pre -int (J) = J .
- (iii) PN Generalized Pre -int (PN Generalized Pre -int (J)) = PN Generalized Pre -int (J)
- (iv) If $J \subseteq K$ then PN Generalized Pre -int (J) \subseteq PN Generalized Pre -int (K)

Proof:

(i) By Definition 3.2.12, PN Generalized Pre -int (J) = $\cap\{K/ K$ is a PN Generalized Pre *Open* set and $K \subseteq J\}$. This implies $J \subseteq$ PN Generalized Pre -int (J). Thus (i) holds.

(ii) Suppose PN Generalized Pre -int (J) = J . Then $\cup\{K/ K$ is a PN Generalized Pre *Open* set and $K \subseteq J\} = J$. This implies that J is a PN Generalized Pre *Open* set in (Z, τ_{PN}) .

Conversely, suppose J is a PN Generalized Pre *Open* set in (Z, τ_{PN}) . Then $\cup\{K/ K$ is a PN Generalized Pre *Open* set and $K \subseteq J\} = J$. Therefore, by Definition 3.2.12, PN Generalized Pre -int (J) = J . Thus (ii) holds.

(iii) For any PN set J , PN Generalized Pre -int (J) is a PN Generalized Pre *Open* set in (Z, τ_{PN}) . Using (ii) we get, PN Generalized Pre -int (PN Generalized Pre -int (J)) = PN Generalized Pre -int (J). Thus (iii) holds.

(iv) Let $J \subseteq K$. Then PN Generalized Pre -int (J) $\subseteq J \subseteq K$. From this we get PN Generalized Pre -int (J) $\subseteq K$. This implies PN Generalized Pre -int (PN Generalized Pre -int (J)) \subseteq PN Generalized Pre -int (K). Therefore by (iii) of this proposition PN Generalized Pre -int (PN Generalized Pre -int (J)) = PN Generalized Pre -int (J). Hence we get PN Generalized Pre -int (J) \subseteq PN Generalized Pre -int (K). Thus (iv) holds.

Theorem 3.2.1 5 Let G be a PN Generalized Pre *Closed* set in (Z, τ_{PN}) and $G \subseteq H \subseteq$ PN Pre -cl (G), then H is a PN Generalized Pre *Closed* set in (Z, τ_{PN}) .

Proof:

Let G be a PN Generalized Pre *Closed* set in (Z, τ_{PN}) . Then PN Pre -cl (G) $\subseteq R$ whenever $G \subseteq R$ where R is a PN *Open* set in (Z, τ_{PN}) . Now by hypothesis, $G \subseteq H \subseteq$ PN Pre -cl (G). This implies $H \subseteq$ PN Pre -cl (G) $\subseteq R$. Also PN Pre -cl (H) \subseteq PN Pre -cl (PN Pre -cl (G)) = PN Pre -cl (G). Thus we get, PN Pre -cl (H) \subseteq PN Pre -cl (G) $\subseteq R$. Hence PN Pre -cl (H) $\subseteq R$ whenever $H \subseteq R$. Therefore, H is a PN Generalized Pre *Closed* set in (Z, τ_{PN}) .

Theorem 3.2.16 Consider J a PN Generalized Pre *Open* set in (Z, τ_{PN}) and PN Pre -int(J) $\subseteq L \subseteq J$, then L is a PN Generalized Pre *Open* set in (Z, τ_{PN}) .

Proof:

Consider J a PN Generalized Pre *Open* set in (Z, τ_{PN}) . Then $H \subseteq$ PN Pre -int (J) whenever $H \subseteq J$ where H is a PN *Closed* set in (Z, τ_{PN}) . Now by hypothesis, PN Pre -int (J) $\subseteq L \subseteq J$. This implies $H \subseteq$ PN Pre -int (J) $\subseteq L$. Also PN Pre -int (L) \supseteq PN Pre -int (PN Pre -int (J)) = PN Pre -int (J). Thus we get PN Pre -int (L) \supseteq PN Pre -int (J) $\supseteq H$. Hence PN Pre -int (L) $\supseteq H$ whenever $L \supseteq H$. Therefore, L is a PN Generalized Pre *Open* set in (Z, τ_{PN}) .

Proposition 3.2.1 7 Consider J a PN set over a PN Topological space (Z, τ_{PN}) . Then

- (i) [PN Generalized Pre - int J]^C = PN Generalized Pre - cl J ^C
- (ii) [PN Generalized Pre - cl J]^C = PN Generalized Pre - int J ^C

Proof:

(i) Consider J a PN set over a PN Topological space (Z, τ_{PN}) . Now, PN Generalized Pre - int $J = \cup\{H/ H$ is a PN Generalized Pre *Open* set and $H \subseteq J\}$. Then [PN Generalized Pre - int J]^C = $[\cup\{H/ H$ is a PN Generalized Pre *Open* set and $H \subseteq J\}]^C = \cap\{H^C/ H^C$ is a PN Generalized Pre *Closed* set and $H^C \supseteq J^C\}$. Taking H^C as R , we get, [PN Generalized Pre - int J]^C = $\cap\{R/ R$ is a PN Generalized Pre *Closed* set and $R \supseteq J^C\}$. Thus, [PN Generalized Pre - int J]^C = PN Generalized Pre - cl J ^C.

(ii) Consider J a PN set over a PN Topological space (Z, τ_{PN}) . Now, PN Generalized Pre - cl $J = \cap\{G/ G$ is a PN Generalized Pre *Closed* set and $G \supseteq J\}$. Then [PN Generalized Pre - cl J]^C = $[\cap\{G/ G$ is a PN Generalized Pre *Closed* set and $G \supseteq J\}]^C = \cup\{G^C/ G^C$ is a PN Generalized Pre *Open* set and $G^C \subseteq J^C\}$. Taking G^C as R , we get, [PN Generalized Pre - cl J]^C = $\cup\{R/ R$ is a PN Generalized Pre *Open* set and $R \subseteq J^C\}$. Thus, [PN Generalized Pre - cl J]^C = PN Generalized Pre - int J ^C.

Theorem 3.2.1 8 In a PN Topological Space (Z, τ_{PN}) , Intersection of two PN Generalized Pre *Closed* Set is again a PN Generalized Pre *Closed* set.

Proof:

Consider S and R be two PN Generalized Pre *Closed* Sets. Then PN Pre -cl (S) $\subseteq M$ whenever $S \subseteq M$ where M is a PN *Open* set in (Z, τ_{PN}) and PN Pre -cl (R) $\subseteq M$ whenever $R \subseteq M$ where M is a PN *Open* set in (Z, τ_{PN}) . PN Pre -cl ($S \cap R$) \subseteq (PN Pre -cl S) \cap (PN Pre -cl R). Since PN Pre -cl (S) $\subseteq M$ and PN Pre -cl (R) $\subseteq M$ we get, PN Pre -cl ($S \cap R$) \subseteq PN Pre -cl (S) \cap PN Pre -cl (R) $\subseteq M$ whenever $S \cap R \subseteq M$ where M is a PN *Open* set in (Z, τ_{PN}) . Thus $S \cap R$ is a PN Generalized Pre *Closed* set.

Theorem 3.2.19 In a PN Topological Space (Z, τ_{PN}) , Union of two PN Generalized PreOpen Set is again a PN Generalized Pre Open set.

Proof:

Consider G and H be two PN Generalized Pre Open Sets. Then $M \subseteq \text{PN Pre-int}(G)$ whenever $M \subseteq G$ where M is a PN Closed set in (Z, τ_{PN}) and $M \subseteq \text{PN Pre-int}(H)$ whenever $M \subseteq H$ where M is a PN Closed set in (Z, τ_{PN}) . $\text{PN Pre-int}(G \cup H) \supseteq (\text{PN Pre-int}(G) \cup \text{PN Pre-int}(H))$. Since $M \subseteq \text{PN Pre-int}(G)$ and $M \subseteq \text{PN Pre-int}(H)$ we get, $M \subseteq (\text{PN Pre-int}(G) \cup \text{PN Pre-int}(H)) \subseteq \text{PN Pre-int}(G \cup H)$ whenever $M \subseteq G \cup H$ where M is a PN Closed set in (Z, τ_{PN}) . Thus $G \cup H$ is a PN Generalized Pre Open set.

Definition 3.2.20 A PN set M is taken from PN Topological Space (Z, τ_{PN}) . Then PN Generalized Pre frontier of M in (Z, τ_{PN}) is defined as PN Generalized Pre frontier $(M) = \text{PN Generalized Pre-cl}(M) \cap \text{PN Generalized Pre-cl}(M^C)$

Definition 3.2.21 A PN set M is taken from PN Topological Space (Z, τ_{PN}) . Then PN Generalized Pre exterior of M in (Z, τ_{PN}) is defined as PN Generalized Pre exterior $(M) = \text{PN Generalized Pre-int}(M^C)$.

4 Conclusion

The Pentapartitioned Neutrosophic Generalized Pre Open and Closed sets are defined in this study. In order to comprehend the concept of Pentapartitioned Neutrosophic Generalized Pre Open and Closed sets, numerous theorems and propositions were also investigated. Additionally, the exterior and frontier of a Pentapartitioned Neutrosophic set were the subject of this study. This will lead to further the investigation of generalized set continuity and connectedness in Pentapartitioned Neutrosophic Topological spaces.

Declaration

Presented in 9th INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE ON DISCRETE MATHEMATICS AND MATHEMATICAL MODELLING IN DIGITAL ERA (ICDMMMDE-2023) during March 23-25, 2023, Organized by the Department of Mathematics, The Gandhigram Rural Institute (Deemed to be University), Gandhigram - 624302, Dindigul, Tamil Nadu, India. ICDMMMDE-23 was supported by: GRI-DTBU, CSIR.

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